

Synthesis and CNS Activity of Some Fluorine Containing Pyrazolo[5,1-c][1,2,4]Triazines

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Seven new fluorinated pyrazolo[5,1-c][1,2,4]triazines have been synthesized by the condensation of pyrazole diazonium salt with 1,3-diketones in aqueous buffered solution. An intermediate is obtained, which on thermal cyclization in glacial acetic acid, gave pyrazolo[5,1-c][1,2,4]triazines. These compounds have been characterized by ir, pmr, and ^{19}F -nmr spectral studies. Most of the compounds display significant anti-inflammatory activity.

PYRAZOLO[5,1-c][1,2,4]triazines and their derivatives have been the object of extensive investigation because of their antitumour properties¹. Initially, triazine derivatives have been investigated for their antibacterial activity by Mamalis *et al*². In 1974, Novinson *et al*³ reported synthesis and biological properties of pyrazolo[5,1-c][1,2,4]triazines. Pyrazolo[1,5-a][1,3,5]triazines are useful as 3',5'-cyclic AMP phosphodiesterase inhibitor and are 10-160 times as active as theophylline^{4,5}. In view of such biological activity associated with pyrazolo[5,1-c][1,2,4]triazines, fluorine containing analogues of pyrazolo-triazines have been synthesized as possible psychopharmacological agents. These were synthesized by the condensation of pyrazole diazonium salt with appropriate 1,3-diketones in an aqueous buffered (sodium acetate) solution. An intermediate (3) was obtained which on thermal cyclization in glacial acetic acid gave pyrazolo[5,1-c][1,2,4]triazines. Pyrazole diazonium salt was obtained by the diazotization of 3-amino-4-phenylpyrazole with sodium nitrite at 0°C. When the diazonium salt was coupled with unsymmetrical

fluorinated 1,3-diketones, two isomeric pyrazolo[5,1-c][1,2,4]triazines could (4) and (5) be obtained. However, only the (4) isomer was obtained in a good yield due to the direction of enolization of 1,3-diketones being towards aryl group⁷.

Experimental

3-Amino-4-phenylpyrazole: A mixture of α -formylphenylacetonitrile (0.15 mole; 22.0 g), hydrazine hydrate (0.25 mole; 12.0 g) and glacial acetic acid (19 ml) was refluxed in dry benzene (200 ml) for 6 hr and water was removed azeotropically. Mixture was then cooled and treated with hydrochloric acid (18%) and filtered. The aqueous layer was separated and when neutralized with ammonium hydroxide, gave a solid compound, which was crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 175° (lit.¹¹ m.p. 174-6°), yield 17.5 g (74%).

3-Diazo-4-phenylpyrazole: Diazotization of 3-amino-4-phenylpyrazole (0.01 mole; 1.60 g) was done in hydrochloric acid (3 ml) with sodium nitrite solution (0.01 mole; 8 g) at 0°. A yellow crystalline precipitate was obtained, m.p. 160°, which was used without further purification, yield 1.68 g (81%).

1,3-Diketones: 1-(4-Fluorophenyl)-3-phenylpropane-1,3-dione, 1-(4-fluorophenyl)butane-1,3-dione, 4,4,4-trifluoro-1-(3-fluoro-4-methoxyphenyl)butane-1,3-dione, 4,4,5,5-pentafluoro-1-(3-fluoro-4-methoxyphenyl)pentane-1,3-dione, 1-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)butane-1,3-dione, 4,4,4-trifluoro-1-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)butane-1,3-dione and 1-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)-3-phenylpropane-1,3-dione were prepared by the condensation of the appropriate fluorinated acetophenone (0.1 mole) with a suitable ester (0.2 mole) in the presence of sodium amide (0.2 mole) in dry solvent ether according to the methods of Joshi *et al*^{7,12}.

3-Acetyl-4,8-disubstitutedpyrazolo[5,1-c][1,2,4]triazines: Pyrazolo triazines were prepared by the method of Novinson *et al*¹³. A methanolic solution

Scheme 1

R = CH₃, CF₃, C₆F₅, C₆H₅;

R' = 4-F.C₆H₄, 3-F-4-OCH₃.C₆H₄, 3-Cl-4-F.C₆H₄.

TABLE 1—PYRAZOLO[5,1-c][1,2,4]TRIAZINES. EXPERIMENTAL, DETAILS AND PHYSICAL DATA

No.	3-Diazo 4-phenyl pyrazole (g)	1,3-Di- ketone (g)	Time of reflux- ing (hr)	Yield (%)	m.p. °C	R	R'	Molecular formula	Nitrogen % Found/ (Calcd.)
4a	2.0	1.8	7	70	153	CH ₃	4-F.C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ FN ₄ O	16.63 (16.96)
4b	2.0	2.4	8	65	168	C ₆ H ₅	4-F.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ FN ₄ O	14.10 (14.21)
4c	2.0	2.6	6	60	160	CF ₃	3-F-4-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ F ₄ N ₄ O ₂	19.21 (18.46)
4d	2.0	3.2	7	70	154	C ₆ F ₅	3-F-4-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ F ₆ N ₄ O ₂	12.00 (12.01)
4e	2.0	2.1	7	74	165	CH ₃	3-Cl-4-F.C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ ClFN ₄ O	15.18 (15.27)
4f	2.0	2.6	8	65	176	CF ₃	3-Cl-4-F.C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₀ H ₉ ClF ₃ N ₄ O	13.20 (13.31)
4g	2.0	2.7	7	60	185	C ₆ H ₅	3-Cl-4-F.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₄ H ₁₄ ClFN ₄ O	13.01 (13.06)

of 1,3-diketone (0.01 mole) was added to a freshly prepared solution of 3-diazo-4-phenylpyrazole (0.01 mole ; 2.1 g) in methanol, followed by the addition of sodium acetate solution (3 g in 10 ml water) at 5°. The mixture was allowed to stand at this temperature for 24 hr. The resulting intermediate was filtered, dried and cyclized by refluxing in glacial acetic acid for 6-8 hr.

All pyrazolo[5,1-c][1,2,4]triazines listed in Table 1 were prepared in a similar manner. The details of the amount of the different reactants, time of refluxing, yield, m.p. and physical data are recorded in Table 1.

Spectral characterization :

In ir spectra, sharp absorption bands were observed in the region 1640-1700 cm⁻¹ due to >C=O group, 1570-1620 cm⁻¹ due to >C=N group, 1560 cm⁻¹ due to -N=N group, 1160-1180 cm⁻¹ due to >C-N group and 1180-1500 cm⁻¹ due to >C-F and CF₃ groups. PMR spectra in trifluoroacetic acid showed characteristic resonance signals in the range of δ 2.5-3.0 ppm due to -CH₃ group (s, 3H), δ 3.0-4.0 ppm due to -OCH₃ group (s, OCH₃) and aromatic protons in the range of δ 7.5-8.5 ppm. Disappearance of methine (=CH-) as well

OH

as enolic (-C=) proton signals of 1,3-diketone and >NH proton signal of 3-diazo-4-phenylpyrazole provides strong evidence for the formation of pyrazolo[5,1-c][1,2,4]triazines. The presence of fluorine and trifluoromethyl group in pyrazolo triazines was confirmed by ¹⁹F-nmr spectra. The presence of fluorine in aryl ring was observed in the region of δ 30-40 ppm and CF₃ group at δ -10 to 5 ppm from the external standard (TFA).

Evaluation of CNS activity in mice :

Compound Nos. 4a, d, e and f were screened for CNS activity on different parameters in mice. All

the compounds were administered intraperitoneally (i.p.) as suspension in gum acacia.

Gross effects :

The animals were observed for 2 hr after drug administration for any evidence of CNS stimulation or depression or any autonomic effect by the method of Dhar *et al*⁸. This involved noting the effect on (i) spontaneous motor activity, (ii) certain reflexes, e.g., righting, corneal and pinnal, (iii) muscle tone (reduced and catalepsy), (iv) ataxia and writhing, (v) eyes (pupiles and ptosis), (vi) respiration and (vii) observing them for the occurrence of tremor, convulsions, Straub's tail, piloerection. At different dose levels, SMA, respiration and reactivity towards sound and touch decrease, writhing is present and animals become less active. Mortality is "nil" within 24 hr ; hence they act as mild CNS depressant. Approximate LD₅₀ is greater than 1000 mg/kg.

Special tests :

Analgesic (tail pinch method⁹) activity was not found at a dose of 200 mg/kg. Compound No. 4d exhibited 20% protection of electric shock in anti-convulsant (SMES test)¹⁰ activity at a dose of 200 mg/kg.

Carrageenan induced oedema was produced in albino rats. Compound Nos. 4d, e and f exhibited significant anti-inflammatory activity (18%, 20%, 30%) with indomethacin as a reference compound (inhibition is 40-50% at a dose level of ~ 4 mg/kg).

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